

IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND CORRECTION OF SPEECH OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN, DYSGRAFIA ON THE BASIS OF VIOLATIONS OF LANGUAGE ANALYSIS AND SYNTHESIS

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ANNOTATION

This article v razvitii i korrektsii rechi detey doshkolnogo vozrasta, disgrafii na pochve narusheniya yazykovogo analiza i rechi detey doshkolnogo vozrasta, disgrafii na pochve narusheniya yazykovogo analiza i is covered on the basis of scientific approaches.

Keyword: *dysgraphia, trudnosti v ovladenii pismom, akusticheskaya disgrafia-characteristics narushenem fonematicallyego raspoznavaniya zvukov, optical disgrafia, differentiation smeshivaemykh bukv, razvivat fonematically slux, influence, influence, corporate components.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Настоящая статья в развитии и коррекции речи детей дошкольного возраста, дисграфии на почве нарушения языкового анализа и речи детей дошкольного возраста, дисграфии на почве нарушения языкового анализа и освещена на основе научных подходов.

Ключевые слова: *дисграфия, трудности в овладении письмом, акустическая дисграфия – характеризуется нарушением фонематического распознавания звуков, оптическая дисграфия, дифференциация смешиваемых букв, развивать фонематический слух, аффрикат и компонентов, коррекции артикуляторно-акустической дисграфии.*

Dysgraphia is a violation of the writing process, manifested in repetitive, persistent errors, which are due to unformed higher mental activity involved in the writing process.

This violation is an obstacle for students to master the literacy and grammar of the language. A child masters written speech by the time he enters school or directly in the first grade. In order for this type of speech to form without much difficulty, it is necessary to master the basis of written speech.

It may include:

1. Correctly formed oral speech. Ability for analytical and synthetic speech activity: division into words, syllables, sounds and synthesis.
2. Developed perception: spatial, visual-spatial gnosis, somato-spatial sensations, knowledge of the body scheme.
3. Formation of the motor sphere.
4. Ability to self-regulation.
5. Formation of abstract thinking.

If this basis is violated, then there may be violations of written speech.

There are 4 groups of writing disorders, which are age-specific:

1. Difficulties in mastering writing. Occurs in the preparatory group at 6–7 years old and in the first grade, manifests itself in a fuzzy knowledge of the alphabet. Children experience difficulties in translating sound into letters, and in the transition from printed to written letters, in addition, they experience difficulties in sound-letter analysis and synthesis.
2. Violation of the formation of the writing process. It occurs in grades 1–2 at 7–8 years old, when children mix printed and written letters, skip syllables, words.
3. Dysgraphia. Numerous persistent, repetitive writing errors. These errors arise due to the lack of formation or disturbance of mental functions (motor, sensory, speech, violation of the mechanisms of organization of activity) that ensure the process of writing. The diagnosis is made by a speech therapist when the child has mastered the technique of writing, at 8–8.5 years old.

- It is worth noting that not always written errors are a sign of a violation of written speech. They may appear due to a special psycho-physiological state (illness, fatigue, emotional stress, type of written work (for example, only on a test due to strong excitement)).

- Causes of dysgraphia

- Despite in-depth study, the causes of dysgraphia have not been clarified with absolute accuracy even today. But certain data is still available.

- • Biological causes: heredity, damage or underdevelopment of the brain at different periods of child development, pathology of pregnancy, fetal trauma, asphyxia, serious somatic diseases, infections that affect the nervous system.

- • Socio-psychological causes: hospitalism syndrome (disorders caused by a person's long stay in a hospital away from home and family), pedagogical neglect, lack of verbal contacts, upbringing in bilingual families.

- • Social and environmental reasons: overestimated requirements for literacy in relation to the child, incorrectly defined (too early) age of literacy training, incorrectly chosen pace and teaching methods.

- As you know, a person begins to master the skills of writing when all the components of his oral speech are adequately formed: sound pronunciation, lexical and grammatical component, phonetic perception, speech coherence. If, during the formation of the brain, the violations indicated above occurred, the risk of developing dysgraphia is very high.

It is useful to play a historian with your child - when the child writes letters with pen and ink. The choice of conventional writing tools must be approached wisely. It is recommended to buy pens, pencils and felt-tip pens with a rough or uneven body, because they massage the distal ends of the fingers, whereby additional signals are sent to the brain.

In fact, there are many options for preventing and working out writing deviations, but all of them must be discussed with a speech therapist without fail. Classes should

be systematic, but short; Be sure to give your child the opportunity to relax, play and do things they love.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Л.С. Волкова. *Логопедия: Учебник для студентов дефектологических факультетов педагогических высш. учеб. Заведений – Владос, 2009. – 703*
2. Н.А. Горяева. *Твоя мастерская. Рабочая тетрадь. Изобразительное искусство 2класс – Просвещение, 2013. – 48*
3. Е. А. Медведева, И. Ю. Левченко, Л. Н. Комиссарова, Т. А. Добровольская. *Артпедагогика и арт-терапия в специальном образовании: Учебник для студентов средних и высших педагогических учебных заведений - Издательский центр «Академия», 2003. – 248*
4. Е.В. Мазанова. *Упражнения по профилактики и коррекции оптической дисграфии. Альбом в 2 частях – Москва, 2006. -62*
5. Акрамова Х. (2020). *Текст научной работы на тему «Формирование коктейльных навыков у школьников с задержкой психического развития на основе компьютерных технологий». Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 1(16), 1-9. извлечено от https://science.i-edu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/4013*
6. Акрамова, Х. (2020). *Коррекционно-педагогические обобщенности формирования навыков здорового образа жизни у детей с умственной отсталостью в семейных условиях. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 15(1). извлечено от https://science.i-edu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/918*
7. Акрамова, Х. (2020). *Социально-педагогическая работа с детьми дошкольного возраста. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 7(1). извлечено от https://science.i-edu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/674*